

USE OF VISUAL AID TO TEACH SCHOOL STUDENTS**Botirova Hakima**

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Abstract This article discusses the benefits of using visual aids in teaching, including how they can help students understand abstract concepts, retain information better, and make learning more engaging and fun. The article also provides examples of different types of visual aids and best practices for using them effectively

Key words: Visual aids, teaching, learning, retention, engagement, abstract concepts, pictures, diagrams, charts, videos, animations, physical objects, best practices.

Main part**Visual aids for school students**

Visual aids have been used for many years to enhance the learning experience of students. They are an effective tool that allows educators to present information in a way that is easy to understand and remember. Visual aids can be anything from pictures, diagrams, charts, videos, and even physical objects. When used properly, visual aids can help students grasp complex concepts, improve their retention of information, and make learning more engaging and fun.

One of the most significant advantages of using visual aids in teaching is that they help students understand abstract concepts. For example, if a teacher is trying to explain the concept of gravity, they can use a video or animation that shows how objects fall towards the earth. This helps students visualize the concept and understand it better than simply reading about it in a textbook. Similarly, a diagram or chart can help students understand complex processes such as photosynthesis or the water cycle.

Visual aids also help students retain information better. Studies have shown that people remember more of what they see than what they hear or read. When teachers use visual aids in their lessons, students are more likely to remember the information presented. This is because visual aids help students create mental images that they can recall later.

Another advantage of using visual aids in teaching is that they make learning more engaging and fun. Students are naturally drawn to colorful and interesting visuals, which makes them more likely to pay attention during lessons. Visual aids can also be used to create interactive learning experiences, such as virtual field trips or simulations, which can be much more engaging than traditional lectures or readings.

There are many different types of visual aids that teachers can use in their lessons. Some examples include:

- Pictures and photographs: These can be used to illustrate concepts or provide examples.
- Diagrams and charts: These can be used to show relationships between different concepts or data.
- Videos and animations: These can be used to demonstrate processes or concepts in action.
- Physical objects: These can be used to provide hands-on learning experiences.

To use visual aids effectively, teachers should follow some best practices. First, they should choose visual aids that are relevant and appropriate for the topic being taught. They should also ensure that the visual aids are clear and easy to understand. Teachers should also use visual aids sparingly and strategically, as too many visuals can be overwhelming and distract from the lesson.

Conclusion In conclusion, visual aids are a valuable tool that can enhance the learning experience of students. They help students understand complex concepts, improve retention of information, and make learning more engaging and

fun. Teachers should use visual aids strategically and follow best practices to ensure they are effective in their lessons. With the right use of visual aids, teachers can create a more effective and enjoyable learning experience for their students.

References:

1. Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2016). *E-learning and the science of instruction: Proven guidelines for consumers and designers of multimedia learning*. John Wiley & Sons.
2. Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mayer, R. E., & Moreno, R. (2003). Nine ways to reduce cognitive load in multimedia learning. *Educational psychologist*, 38(1), 43-52.
3. Paivio, A. (1971). *Imagery and verbal processes*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
4. Tversky, B., Morrison, J. B., & Betrancourt, M. (2002). Animation: can it facilitate?. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 57(4), 247-262.
5. Woolfolk, A., Winne, P. H., & Perry, N. E. (2016). *Educational psychology*. Pearson Education.